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Note

Integrating the response to HIV with the response for all MDGs: Responding to the economic crisis

Millennium Development Goals (MDG) MDGs were already behind their targets and the whole international community fears a severe setback in progresses achieved so far. The human consequences of the crisis will be particularly catastrophic for countries with no social protection net. All international and domestic efforts should be oriented to contain adverse effects on populations. Supporting all MDGs made the consensus among all donors and financing the Response to HIV fully goes in this line.

As UNSG Ban Ki-Moon pointed « *Halting and reversing the spread of AIDS is not only a goal in itself; it is a prerequisite for reaching almost all the others* »¹.

The following section analyzes the interaction between each MDG, the economic crisis and the HIV response..

MDG1 Eradicate extreme poverty and hunger

There is a complex two-sided relationship between poverty and HIV with inequality being the vehicle.

First, the economic crisis will increase the number of people and families falling into poverty and reduce the capacity of vulnerable households to deal with the impacts of HIV infection. Some 65 million people will fall below the \$2-a-day poverty line. It is estimated that the current crisis will represent a loss or 20% of the per capita income for poor people in Africa². There are fears that this will lead people to riskier life choices such as working far from home or engaging in commercial sex.

Second, any increase in AIDS would further exacerbate poverty because of its impact on loss of income and higher health expenditures for affected households.

It is important to understand the impact the economic crisis might have on poverty strategies and how the HIV-related activities can be made more resilient. UN Joint teams are efficient mechanisms that can support countries and donors to maintain and expand their programmes in favour of vulnerable groups, including those living with AIDS and high-risk groups. The UN

¹ Secretary-General speaking at the General Assembly High Level Meeting on HIV/AIDS, June08

² UNESCO, Global Monitoring Report

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system will need a country-level monitoring system to assess vulnerability and UNAIDS will need to ensure that HIV is integrated into it.

MDG2 Achieve universal primary education

Ensuring children's access to school is a determinant aspect of HIV prevention as higher levels of education are associated with safer sexual behaviour and delayed sexual debut and reduce girls' vulnerability to HIV³.

In previous financial and economic crises infant mortality rates rose and school enrolment dropped. The economic downturn will introduce more financial constraints which can limit children's educational opportunities since there is evidence that schooling is atypically sensitive to fluctuations in household income⁴.

Social protection, including targeted cash support that could reach HIV-affected households would significantly increase assistance to children. UNAIDS, together with cosponsoring agencies, should promote social protection programmes, particularly those providing cash transfers to low income households without explicit targeting to HIV-affected households (in order to avoid stigma⁵). UNICEF has called for an "AIDS sensitive, but not AIDS exclusive" approach⁶.

Despite the economic crisis; it is of particular importance for MDG2 to insure that access to HIV treatment and care are improved, as it has been shown that children spend 20% more time at school and experience sharp improvements in their nutritional status once HIV-positive adult in the household starts on ARV treatment⁷.

MDG3 Promote gender equality and empower women

This Goal is probably the most in jeopardy due to the economic crisis as women develop coping strategies that lead to exacerbate their own vulnerability in order to prevent the one of their children or household. The crisis is likely to produce clear gender-specific impacts such as falls in women's income, in school attendance for girls and a rise in infant mortality rates for girls⁸.

Gender inequality presents women and girls with barriers and disadvantages in terms of rights, resources and opportunities, resulting in women being more dependent on men in their relationships. These gender inequalities contribute to a higher risk of exposure to HIV for women and girls. Progress in gender equality is therefore progress in the response to HIV.

Progress in responding to the HIV epidemic has also contributed to new gender norms, as countries are now routinely monitored on gender equity as part of the national HIV programme. Further, HIV prevention activities have stimulated the commitments of governments, communities and parents to address the sexual and reproductive health needs of girls and women.

In times of economic slowdown, women in most regions of the world are particularly at risk because they own fewer assets and have less access to credit. UNAIDS should push for

³ P. Piot, Achieving the MDGs: Why the AIDS response counts, 2008

⁴ P.F. Orazem, P. Glewwe and H. Patrinos, The benefits and costs of alternative strategies to improve educational outcomes, Copenhagen consensus, 2008

⁵ Targeted cash support with criteria like low income, as well as household including orphan, would reach many HIV-related households (UNICEF 2007)

⁶ UNICEF policy Brief – HIV and AIDS, draft version April 2009

⁷ Thirumurthy, Zivin, Goldstein, AIDS treatment and intra-household resource allocations : Children's nutrition and school in Kenya, CGD, 2007

⁸ Buvinic M, World Bank, at the Economic and Social Council, Commission on the Status of Women, March 2009

microfinancing options for women which have high cost-benefit ratios⁹ and promote gender equality and empowerment of women. Reducing women's financial vulnerability through microfinance enables them to command greater bargaining power in the household.

MDG4 Reduce child mortality

UNICEF has pointed out that infant mortality rate rose and school enrolment dropped during previous financial and economic crises. In a time of budget contraction, it is of particular importance to insure that antenatal care and drugs are made available in order to prevent mother-to-child HIV transmission, particularly in generalised high prevalence countries like Botswana, Swaziland and Zimbabwe.

AIDS is among the five diseases¹⁰ that account for about 50 per cent of under-five deaths. It is estimated that 370.000 children became infected with HIV in 2007, bringing the number of children living with HIV to 2 million in 2007.

It is therefore of primary importance for MDG4 to scale up prevention of mother-to-child transmission and to make available paediatric ART, as without treatment, about half of children with perinatal infection will die by age two¹¹. Such treatments for children are proven to be particularly effective in resource-poor settings.

MDG5 Improve maternal health

One woman dies every minute around the world from pregnancy or childbirth complications. Most obstetric services in developing regions are already facing chronic shortages in health workers and proper equipment. There are fears that the economic crisis will further limit these scarce resources and threaten the attainment of this goal.

For most low and middle-income countries, a budgetary crisis will most likely follow the current global economic crisis. An effective response to HIV can provide resources that can also contribute towards meeting this Goal. As pointed out by Physicians for Human Rights, an integrated response that addresses both HIV infection risk and reproductive health for women is a practical, efficient and effective way to improve women's access to health services¹².

Integrating family planning and voluntary counselling and testing (VCT) provides multiple entry points to the health system, while expanding the reach and uptake of HIV services. Integration helps break down many of the barriers that users of health and HIV services are facing, such as limited resources, physical distance, stigma and discrimination. Integration of services decreases fragmentation and provides a continuum of care that promotes early detection for HIV¹³. Further, it empowers women to make informed reproductive decisions.

The integration of HIV services with reproductive health has already started in many countries thanks to donors like the PEPFAR and the GFATM and should be scaled-up further during the economic crisis.

MDG6 Combat HIV/AIDS, malaria and other diseases

MDG6 includes the three most serious fatal diseases in low and middle income countries, killing the largest number of 0-5 year children and productive adults. Human capital is a key requirement for economic recovery and all efforts should be focussed to preserve this capacity,

⁹ Elizabeth M King, Stephan Klasen and Maria Porter, *Women and Development*, 2008

¹⁰ The five diseases are: pneumonia, diarrhoea, malaria, measles and AIDS

¹¹ UNAIDS, *Global report 2008*

¹² See: <http://physiciansforhumanrights.org>

¹³: idem¹³ See: <http://physiciansforhumanrights.org>

particularly in low and middle-income countries where the economy relies mainly on labour intensive sectors.

Financing HIV can leverage health services and support the strengthening of basic delivery systems. For example, in the recently published estimates of investment needs for AIDS for the years 2009 and 2010, UNAIDS is calling for 37% of HIV investment needs to be spent on aspects of health system strengthening and cross-cutting activities. This investment is in addition to the; 25% for multisectoral services. The remaining 38% would be targeted to HIV-specific health services¹⁴.

Universal access to HIV prevention, treatment, care and support yields benefits that extend far beyond HIV itself and are further relevant in times of economic contraction. Further, the current economic turmoil emphasises the importance of the opportunity to internalise the lessons learned from HIV, malaria and TB in order to strengthen the approach to all of the health MDGs. One of the key elements of the responses to HIV, Malaria, TB and other diseases, including Avian influenza, is that they have succeeded at expanding a health issue beyond the medical sphere. For example, the following elements generated for HIV could also contribute to the health MDGs:

- Generating innovative and additional financing mechanisms – along the lines of the Global Fund, UNITAID and ProductRED.
- Generating successful global advocacy on health issues: to raise awareness in wealthy countries about health issues in poor countries
- Community mobilisation: community mobilisation has been boosted through the response to the epidemic, in line with the Bamako initiative. This momentum could carry over to other MDGs.
- Partnership: the response to HIV gave birth to new levels of partnership between private and public actors that could apply to other development issues.

MDG7 Ensure environmental sustainability

Like the response to HIV, sustaining our environment and natural resources implies a continuous involvement over time with most outcomes occurring in the long term.

In time of economic crisis, strong political commitment is needed for environmental sustainability as for HIV. Short term decisions cannot disregard long term emergencies. Reducing investments in the environment or the responding to HIV would lead to higher long term costs.

MDG8 Develop a global partnership for development

Perhaps more than any other issue in our time, HIV has highlighted global and economic inequalities, and has galvanised action in international development. HIV has helped place people at the centre of development¹⁵.

Access to affordable essential drugs in developing countries is a critical target of this MDG as in most low and middle-income countries, the availability of drugs and medicines is often very poor. HIV financing has become an important channel for improving the procurement and distribution of essential drugs, in addition to HIV, tuberculosis and malaria medicines, to public health facilities¹⁶. In addition, HIV has enabled innovative South-South partnership like the Brazil-Mozambique cooperation for the construction of a \$23 million plant to produce generic drugs for the treatment of AIDS; the most ambitious foreign assistance project ever launched by Brazil.

¹⁴ The remaining 25% to be targeted to multisectoral services¹⁴ UNAIDS, What countries needs, Investments needed for 2010 targets, 2009; http://data.unaids.org/pub/Report/2009/20090210_investments_needed_2010_en.pdf

¹⁵ UNAIDS global Report 2008, http://www.unaids.org/en/KnowledgeCentre/HIVData/GlobalReport/2008/2008_Global_report.asp

¹⁶ United Nations, The Millennium Development Goals Report 2008

The fulfilment of the Paris Declaration on Aid Effectiveness is getting more and more pressing as the ODA is becoming under pressure due to the global financial and economic crisis. HIV has championed partnership and country-owned development strategies and improved aid effectiveness of the HIV response, thanks to the Three Ones principle. Given the current global context, UNAIDS is committed to making unprecedented efforts in assisting UN Cosponsors and countries to increase further the effectiveness of HIV aid.

In conclusion, HIV is particularly vulnerable to the outcome of the economic crisis, and the attainment of universal access is dependent on progress on all of the other MDGs. Supporting HIV programmes is essential to prevent the rolling back of hard-won gains. In addition, supporting HIV programmes leverages the opportunities to achieve the other MDGs.